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Human	1 MAEPGHSHHLSARVRGRTERRIPRLWRLLWAGTAFQVTQGTGPELHACK	ESEYHYEYTTACDS	TGSRMRVAVPHHTGL	GLTSLPDP	IKGTEGSSFCNAGEFLDMKD	--QSKP	CAEGRYSLGTG	IRFDEWDELPHGFAS	136	
Mouse	1 MAEPGHNPSPARDGGKTERRIPRLWLLWAGTTFQVTLGTGPELHACK	ESEYHFYETACDS	TGSRMRVAVPHSPGL	GLTSLPDP	FVKGTGESSFCNAGEFLDMKD	--QSKP	CAEGRYSLGTG	IRFDEWDELPHGFAS	136	
Zebrafish	1 -----MI VNHVLFSSGTQGVSVIF-----	LLHLLL	TEATELPSCKESDYHF	YTTD	DVLSRMRVAIPNK	PETG	TGLPDP	VKGTGCTFTONEGEFLDMRT	--QECQKCAAGTYS	121
Sea_Anemone	1 -----MGFNI	RGKRI	CF-FV-----	FVAIF	LSPTKGETCKPEQ	IRYDF	TE	DSSDGRYVAVPKTDSCEVAQK	ETROKECTESCKEETYL	118
Human	137 LSANMELDD-----	SAAESTG	NGCTSSKVVPRG	DDYIAS	NTDECTATLMYAV	NLKQSG	----	TNFEY	YYPDSSII	263
Mouse	137 LSANLEVDD-----	SISESTE	NGCTSSKVVPRG	DDYIAS	NTDECTATLMYAV	NLKQSG	----	TNFEY	YYPDSSII	263
Zebrafish	122 HGINMNFQD-----	T-----	YTNCS	NSTWIPK	GDYIAS	NTDECT	STLSYAV	LKKPG	----	244
Sea_Anemone	119 HSPVQYRQYGYDDEF	FSKEKGS	NGSKL	KPLGDS	IGSSG	DECT	SQNL	YAVTL	RNDQ	232
Human	264 IAITGVAYTSECFPK	PKPTI	ADKQ	SSFFK	LIP	ANSYS	NKGET	TS	HOQDP	400
Mouse	264 IAITGVAYTSECFPK	PKPTI	ADKQ	SSFFK	LIP	ANSYS	NKGET	TS	HOQDP	400
Zebrafish	245 IAI	SBVSY	TSECF	PKPTI	YSDP	GAAR	CVPA	ANSYS	NKGA	381
Sea_Anemone	233 I	EVQ	GVAY	TSECF	PKP	AGT	FNDK	MAAA	HQQM	369
Human	401 SYSNGS-DCTRC	PA	TEP	AV	GF	EYK	WNTL	P	N	537
Mouse	401 SYSNGS-DCTHC	PA	TEP	AV	GF	EYK	WNTL	P	N	537
Zebrafish	382 FYSNGT-ECSE	CF	AG	TEP	VV	GF	EYK	W	N	518
Sea_Anemone	370 HYSDEIK	GCQ	CV	YS	TS	VY	DFR	WR	N	502
Human	538 TYI	TE	NT	TS	FT	W	AF	Q	R	671
Mouse	538 TYI	TE	NT	TS	FT	W	AF	Q	R	671
Zebrafish	519 SYL	IK	T	N	S	T	Y	S	W	651
Sea_Anemone	503 D	Y	I	T	S	Q	E	R	T	637
Human	672 NFS	AL	ANT	V	T	L	A	G	P	809
Mouse	672 NFS	AL	AG	T	V	L	A	G	P	809
Zebrafish	652 D	F	S	M	G	N	I	T	G	778
Sea_Anemone	638 D	F	S	D	L	Q	G	V	S	766
Human	810 SGR	ST	I	R	V	R	S	P	O	940
Mouse	810 SGR	ST	I	R	L	R	N	P	M	940
Zebrafish	779 NGR	S	S	I	R	L	R	O	P	909
Sea_Anemone	767 Q	R	T	I	I	V	T	L	K	904
Human	941 YSK	LV	M	N	A	T	L	K	D	1013
Mouse	941 YSK	LV	M	N	A	T	L	K	D	1013
Zebrafish	910 YSK	L	M	M	T	A	G	D	K	982
Sea_Anemone	905 Y	H	R	L	Q	N	A	S	G	995

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